

AI as Moral Device – A reflection on roles and distance

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Ongoing research efforts in the field of engineering and HCI have investigated ways of operationalising human moral decision-making processes and replicate these mechanics in algorithms [3] with the aim of creating independent artificial moral agents. While persuasive and nudging technologies have been successful in creating environments that support certain behaviours while limiting or inhibiting others, second-order ethical design, the design of systems that take and enact ethical stances, is facing challenges on many fronts, posing the question whether true moral artificial agents are indeed possible. While algorithmic machine learning systems are already in use in morally relevant fields, such as in criminal justice cases and to allocate financial opportunities, the question remains whether these agents are considered as possessing their own morality, simply because professionals base their moral judgements on their recommendations. In this position paper I want to discuss whether the creation of artificial moral agents is actually desirable and argue that current efforts to that goal might lead in fact to an increased distancing of people from moral deliberation processes, in particular when it comes to data-driven algorithmic systems, which are considered to embody AI. I base my arguments in ethnographic observations I collected during a series of forecasting workshops organized and facilitated through a Swedish innovation hub and business network. The facilitators described the purpose of the workshops to “gather a diverse group of experts and practitioners to discover and co-create insights and lay ground for future innovations to uncover new ways for harnessing artificial intelligence for sustainability.”

1 AI AS AUTOMATED MORAL ENGAGEMENT PROCESS

Based on the ethnographic observations I identify AI to be assigned three main distinct yet interrelated roles, each automating one part of a moral deliberation process: The role of *insight provider*, which addresses a need of knowing and understanding what is relevant to take into account when making a moral decision, the role of *advisor*, which addresses the needs of providing guidance on how to make a deliberate ethical choice given the relevant insights and lastly the role of the *enforcer*, which addresses the need of knowing how to enact a choice given the situational circumstances. These roles rely on specific properties which are projected onto the system as well as the world: universality of values and systems, the assumption of a finite amount of data through which the system could achieve the status of being “all knowing” and, also as a result of this “all knowing”, a reliable neutrality and objectivity. Together, these three roles are components of an overarching imaginary, in which AI is identified as a singular system calibrated to enable what participants describe as *stable balance and harmony* as the final desirable mode of the envisioned future.

1.1 AI as insight provider

As *insight provider*, AI systems are described helping humanity to “zoom out” from our own perspective towards “the bigger picture” to enable humans to situate themselves within a bigger ecosystem, and see their actions and decisions as connected to broader consequences. In this role the main function of the AI system is to enable a fuzzy notion of all-encompassing understanding, which allows humans to be sure that they are considering everything of relevance when being faced with a moral dilemma. In this functionality, AI augments the implied limited understanding of complexity by humans, who are constrained in their capabilities to oversee broader complexity due to their own restrictive positionality and hence unable to consider the amount of data necessary to gain overarching insight. This vision of AI takes on a consequentialist orientation and implies that there is a finite amount of data, and impact and consequences can be tracked and predicted to their full extent.

1.2 AI as advisor

As an *advisor*, AI systems are described as being able to make decisions based on this broader insight. AI will either make decisions independently or support decision makers in taking the “right” decision, by providing insights, knowledge, information, and an overview of the consequences of certain decisions. This extends the capabilities of the system from “knowing” more than humans do to also possessing the ability to run decision making processes and having an idea how to deal and interpret the available data and turn it into decision guiding knowledge. As a universal and globally connected system, this envisioned AI systems will act on universal agreements of values, norms and regulations. Actions and decisions taken by the AI systems are assumed to have the same meaning in any place of the world. Finally, the envisioned AI will be neutral and objective, as it will be globally connected and taking “everything” into account, it will be able to provide unbiased and therefore justified view of the world. This implies that objectivity can be assumed if only the provided data is sufficient.

1.3 AI as enforcer

As an *enforcer*, AI systems are described as agents that act within a stable network of monitoring, automatization, and optimization, which enforces previously made decisions based on the broader picture insight and enacts what has been considered “best”. AI will enable optimization, automation, and constant monitoring by tracking resource consumption and coordinating labor efforts. It will also take over “boring” jobs, to alleviate humans from drudgery. Through tracking and monitoring, this system will provide “full transparency”, in which there is no way to hide “bad actions” or any decision not in line with what the system deems the “correct” way. However, the system as envisioned in the workshop scenarios, would allow for margins of behavior, by allowing negative actions to be compensated with positive ones, and weighing selfish acts against acts performed for the benefit of the global community.

1.4 AI for the greater good

These three roles presuppose, inform and feed into each other – taking the zoomed out, all knowing perspective enables the system to apply its decision-making processes, which guides the enactment of what needs to be automated, optimized and monitored. This enactment then feeds into the knowing, as constant monitoring enables the ongoing and all-reaching data collection. All three parts together are imagined to enable an imaginary of AI-driven “balance and harmony”, vague notion of objective greater good, in which needs, desires and interests across humanity and beyond are integrated into an all-encompassing idea of globally balanced wellbeing among different parties:

- Balance between the individual and the collective, in which case AI limits “selfish” actions, and makes sure that the individual acts in accordance with the good of the greater community.
- Balance between different cultures, in which case AI is used as a political tool to mediate between cultures and groups and take on political tensions. This comes in different flavors within the scenarios – either AI creates a global unifying narrative and story that makes tensions between cultures and communities obsolete, or it enables “true” democracy in which conflicts of interest are resolved in the fairest and most harmonious manner.
- Balance between nature and humans in which AI enforces the interests of “nature” and non-human species in order to force humans to live within the means of the planet and nature.

2 AI AS THE FINAL MORAL DEVICE

In the described imaginary, humanity, or unique human cognitive traits, are mostly defined to creativity and unique original thought, leaving aside important relational components, intellectualizing the contributions humans could possibly make to a desirable future. Jasanoff [4] specifies imaginaries at the intersection of the social and the technical as sociotechnical imaginaries which include “the myriad ways in which scientific and technological visions enter into the assemblages of materiality, meaning, and morality that constitute robust forms of social life”. In these envisionings, AI systems fit particular dimensions of the device paradigm, as introduced by Borgmann [2]. The device paradigm refers to a way of life that is characterized by the use of devices that mediate our experience of the world. These devices are designed to make life easier, more efficient, and more convenient, but they also have the effect of separating us from the direct experience of the world around us. They create a layer of abstraction between us and the world around us, shaping how we perceive and interact with reality. AI follows this narrative of smart devices, beyond smart desire fulfillment, towards a greater good. In this imaginary of AI-driven balance and harmony, AI optimizes away the relational, messy qualities of humanity as it equates them with selfish, unreflective, and non-harmonious behavior, shaping the normative understanding of moral behavior. In this imaginary, AI enables a world in which humans can remain as they are and do not need to engage in efforts of internal moral growth, as their idiosyncrasies are being externally confined by the AI governed system, controlling these characteristics with paternalistic exposition. In questions of means and ends, AI follows the tendency to focus on the *ends*, the desired outcome, rather than the *means*, the process and recognition of labor and context within which the ends are desired [1]. AI is projected to be the device that will bring the intangible good of balance and harmony, while putting the means, the actual process of engaging in ethical reflection, deliberation and responding to fellow humans, behind the glossy exterior of a device. In these AI imaginaries, ethics and morals are being automated and moved behind the neutral and objective dreamed-up AI vision, which removes the interaction with dilemmas and complicated questions rather than enabling deeper intentional engagement with them.

2.1 But whose morality?

The design of moral agents asks the question who should be influenced and guided by these agents? Individual users might be persuaded to opt for more sustainable habits, but these might clash with the bigger infrastructure that these individuals might find themselves in. A keyholder that makes it easier to take the bike rather than the car is not necessarily a device sensitive to the contextual burden placed on the individual in their environment if the city infrastructure is dangerous for cyclists because it favors cars and doesn't provide safe bike paths. Moral agents will always face the contextual interpretation of viable tradeoffs for individuals within bigger systems, which poses the question how individuals are being positioned against the greater good of the community. Considering the device character of the AI narrative, there is no reason to believe that second-order artificial moral agents would attend to structural biases any better than existing systems, which reproduce human biases. We can assume that people who are already not fitting well within the established structures of society might be considered even more “flawed” humans than average and as result, marginalized based on their non-conformity to a hegemonic view of the rational white male will have to be even more “contained”. Without engaging with the political dimensions of underlying social structures, unified approaches to morality are bound to reinforce a global political status quo, in which contestation will be even harder based on moral grounds. This leads me to argue that any efforts towards building agents of second-order moral agency requires a strong orientation towards political power structures, and a sensitivity towards the means which are being potentially erased by providing artificial moral agents.

References

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